

Diagnosis of Rotor Asymmetries in Wound Rotor Induction Machines via PSH Analysis of Vibration Transients

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Abstract—Wound Rotor Induction Machines (WRIMs) are widely utilized in industrial applications with high starting torque. The rotor health of such machines influences the machine efficiency and ultimately, the overall safety and reliability. The monitoring of the housing vibrations represent a highly available manner of holistic diagnosis. Nevertheless, the evaluation of rotor health through vibration signals primarily focuses on steady-state operation and has received comparatively limited investigation when compared with electrical signature analysis. The present paper introduces a novel technique to diagnose rotor winding asymmetries in WRIMs by analysing the transient evolutions of Principal Slot Harmonic (PSH) families. Particularly, an inverter-fed start-up is analysed, which poses increased challenges for rotor defect diagnosis. The methodology exploits the resonance phenomena that arises from the interactions of time evolving forces and natural structural frequencies.

Index Terms—Induction motors, Fault diagnosis, Principal slot harmonics (PSH)

I. INTRODUCTION

Each year, millions of rotating electrical machines undergo repairs exclusively in North America [1], offering a quantitative insight into the allocation of electrical machinery maintenance budgets. Wound Rotor Induction Machines (WRIMs) are widely adopted in heavy industry (e.g., cranes, ball and sag mills, etc.) and energy conversion mechanisms such as wind power production [2]. The malfunction of the rotor circuit significantly undermines system efficiency, potentially leading to catastrophic failure. Particularly, imperfections in auxiliary devices in the rotor circuit (i.e., inverters, slip rings, switches,

etc.) as well as winding short-circuits induce the electromagnetic asymmetry in the machine leading to the malfunction of the system. Therefore, timely and rapid identification of asymmetries in the rotor circuit is a crucial asset for effective maintenance.

The detection of rotor asymmetries by utilizing stator current signals is a widespread technique in literature [3]. Particularly, the analysis both in transient and steady state regimes provides enhanced reliability for the detection [4]. Nevertheless, the utilization of vibration signals for diagnosing and monitoring rotating machinery continues to be the conventional approach, largely due to the numerous standards and practitioners utilizing this physical magnitude [5]. In addition, vibration signals are able to better capture mechanical malfunction related to bearing defects, misalignments, mass unbalances, etc. However, failure mechanisms of electromagnetic nature are also present in the vibration signature. Tsytkin [6] clearly highlights the main components of electromagnetic noise in induction motors, given by the radial forces acting in the stator and oscillations in the electromagnetic torque. Vilchis et al. [7] studied the effects of electromagnetic torque oscillations caused by resistive winding asymmetry in WRIMs. The authors conclude the paper highlighting the importance of twice-slip dependent side-bands around the main components of the torque. The broken rotor bar failure in squirrel cage induction machines (SCIMs) poses a similar nature when compared to winding current asymmetries in WRIMs. Several authors propose the utilization of higher-frequency harmonics to detect broken rotor bars in SCIMs [8], [9]. These works demonstrate the effect of rotor asymmetries on the Principal Slot Harmonics (PSH) affecting the current and vibration signature. The work presented in [10] exploits the mains fed start-up evolution of the PSH side-bands to diagnose broken

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rotor bars. The transient evolution of these harmonics during the start-up covers a wide frequency band ranging from 0 Hz to few kHz in some cases. This brings interesting capabilities such as the amplification of the time evolving signatures when exciting forces and structural natural frequencies match in the frequency domain. The inverter-fed machine case is of particular interest since the diagnosis of rotor asymmetries in the time-frequency domain poses increased complexity as highlighted in works such as [11].

The present work explores the diagnosis of winding asymmetries in WRIMs by analyzing the transient evolutions of electromagnetic components of the vibration spectrum. Particularly, an open-loop inverter-fed case study is analysed, where the slip-dependent electromagnetic components evolve close to each other during the start-up. Special attention is paid to the evolution of the different families of PSH, which contain useful failure information and are likely to excite different structural frequencies. The technique is tested in a laboratory environment where a 0.6 kW WRIM is utilized as a case study. The present paper is organized as follows. Section II synthesizes the main physical principles behind the proposed technique. Section III introduces the laboratory set-up and machine specimen. Section IV presents the steady-state analysis of well-known rotor asymmetry indicators. Section V introduces the analysis of the inverter-fed start-up at rated load by utilizing an efficient time-frequency transformation and a comprehensive quantitative indicator of the failure. Section VI closes and discusses the main outcomes and limitations of the work.

II. THEORETICAL JUSTIFICATION OF THE PROPOSED DIAGNOSIS

The present section justifies the presented diagnosis strategy from a physical perspective. It is based on the phenomenon of rotor fault propagation towards speed fluctuations, which are ultimately affecting the machine slip and the vibration spectrum [3]. Healthy and ideal WRIMs show balanced stator and rotor currents, which possess an equally balanced magnetomotive force (i.e., mmf) wave in the air gap. Thus, the stator fed with a current signal at fundamental frequency f induces a rotor current at a frequency sf , where s represents the motor slip. In the case of an unbalanced rotor winding, a counter rotating field with frequency $-sf$ is generated, which in turn, induces a stator current at $(1 - 2s)f$. The interaction of negative and positive sequence currents in stator and rotor conductors, causes a counter-rotating torque and thus, speed oscillations at $2sf$. Speed oscillations induce the well-known upper current side-band in the stator current at $1 + 2sf$.

Forward and backward mmf waves are reflected in the vibration spectrum in the shape of twice slip components. These are normally tracked as side-bands around rotating frequency during steady-state machine operation as reported in works such as [6], [12]. Nevertheless, the amplitude and detectability of such harmonics strongly depends on the operating regime and the vibration sampling point of the machine. The amplitude of vibration signals sampled in an electrical

machine housing vary depending on the mechanical transfer function between force excitation and acquisition location. Thus, the fault related signature is amplified or attenuated depending on the frequency band of excitation. Time-evolving components are prone to excite different mechanical regions enabling enhanced detection of asymmetry faults as reported in [10].

Rotor-modulated mmf components represent a feasible time-evolving component with useful asymmetry fault signature [8]. These are present in the air gap flux density wave and in radial forces exciting stator-borne vibration, which are measurable through housing vibration acquisition. Particularly, the analysis of PSH located in higher frequency regions of the vibration spectrum, represents a feasible indicator of rotor asymmetries while covering a wide frequency range during the motor start-up. The PSH location is defined by [13]:

$$f_{PSH\pm} = f\left(\frac{R}{p}(1 - s) \pm \nu\right) \quad (1)$$

where R is the number of rotor slots, p is the pole pair number, s represents the slip, and ν is an even integer (i.e., $\nu = 0, 2, 4, 6, \dots$). In the case of inverter-fed WRIMs the transition from null to rated supply frequency represents a feasible scenario for rotor asymmetry fault detection. Note that in the case of inverter-fed induction motors the slip value is constant during the start-up or supply frequency changes, which specially hinders the detection of rotor asymmetries through the usage of well-known indicators during the motor start-up (e.g., phase current side-bands at $1 \pm 2ksf$, $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$). Thus, the tracking of transient PSH families represents a physically valid alternative for rotor asymmetry evaluation if the relationship between rotor slots and pole pairs satisfies the observable PSH requirements [14].

III. EXPERIMENTAL WORK DESCRIPTION

The present section is aimed to describe the laboratory test bench and the machine under test. The machine specimen is a three-phase, 4 pole, 0.6 kW WRIM with single layer rotor and stator slots, and full pitch distributed stator winding. The rated speed is 1450 rpm (i.e., 3.3 % slip) and the rotor is formed by 24 slots with equally distributed three-phase winding. Figure 1 shows the schematic of the test-bench, where the main components and connections are depicted. The machine under test is coupled to a Synchronous Generator (SG) via non-flexible coupling and connected to three resistive loads for dissipation. The load torque regulation is performed by adjusting both the generator field and the load voltage via variable autotransformer (Variac). The acquisition system consists of a 4-channel wave recorder (Yokogawa DL350) that synchronously samples vibration, phase current and phase-to-ground voltage. The vibration is measured by utilizing two accelerometers (PCB352C33) placed in the motor Drive End (DE) at 12 and 3 o'clock positions respectively.

The machine is fed via Variable Frequency Drive (VFD) where the supply frequency is ramped from 0 Hz to 50 Hz in

Fig. 1. Test-bench description

approximately 9 seconds. The machine is controlled in open-loop with a traditional scalar voltage/frequency regulator. This control methodology is a widespread method for induction machine supply frequency regulation and avoids current fluctuation compensation. Note that operation in open-loop control is essential to avoid faulty component compensation. The fault is implemented by connecting a rheostat to one of the rotor phases, creating a resistive winding unbalance in the rotor. This is a common scenario of high resistance connection in industrial application WRIMs as described in [4]. To address the severity of the fault, three scenarios are analyzed, considering the nominal rotor resistance value of 5.1Ω under standstill conditions. In two of these scenarios, additional resistances are connected in series with a rotor phase, corresponding to 30% and 300% of the nominal single-phase resistance representing light and severe asymmetry scenarios respectively.

IV. VIBRATION STEADY-STATE ANALYSIS

The current section focuses on a rigorous examination of established fault indicators, encompassing an analysis of various PSH families. This investigation aims to elucidate the presence and evaluate the extent of the fault up to substantial severity levels. Figure 2 shows the vibration spectrum around the rotating frequency f_r . The well-known side-bands located at $f_r \pm 2sf$ are readily detectable, demonstrating a clear differentiation among the three analyzed fault severity states. Note that minor speed variations are observed in the case of severe asymmetry. This slight difference arises from the challenges associated with manually adjusting the machine operating point under conditions of significant asymmetry (i.e., with heavy speed oscillations).

Figure 3 presents the steady-state analysis of different PSH families including $\nu = 0, 2, 4, 6$ at rated slip. These are the PSH components with higher amplitude for the healthy state. For higher severity levels, side-bands at $k2sf \forall k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ are accentuated around the main PSH locus. As the severity level increases, the energy becomes more dispersed within the

Fig. 2. Vibration spectrum around rated rotating frequency (i.e., 24.16 Hz) for different fault severity levels

side-bands. The main PSH for a high severity level is attenuated, while the value is kept almost unaltered for the light asymmetry state. Nevertheless, the light asymmetry scenario mainly presents the immediate inferior $2sf$ side-band while higher order side-bands are attenuated in the spectrum. Figure 4 exemplifies the observed harmonic spectrum distribution for different levels of rotor electrical asymmetry around the PSH frequency locus.

V. VIBRATION TRANSIENT ANALYSIS

The present section is aimed to the detailed analysis of the transient PSH evolutions during the inverter-fed WRIM start-up. Transient signals are commonly represented in the time-frequency domain to analyse the evolution over time of the different frequency components. The present method is based on the Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT), which represents a simple and computationally efficient manner of time-frequency representation. The STFT is defined by:

Fig. 3. Vibration spectrum around PSH ($\nu = 0, 2, 4, 6$) for different fault severity levels at rated slip, (a) $\nu = 0$, (b) $\nu = 2$, (c) $\nu = 4$, (d) $\nu = 6$

Fig. 4. Observed vibration spectrum variation around PSH locus for different rotor asymmetry severities

$$STFT\{x(t)\} = X(\tau, f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)w(t-\tau)e^{-2\pi fjt} dt \quad (2)$$

where $x(t)$ is the analysed discrete signal, and $w(t-\tau)$ represents the window function where τ symbolizes the center location of the window. Hanning windowing is applied prior Fourier transformation in order to minimize spectral leakage. The time window is selected to capture the slip oscillations at $2sf$. Figure 5 shows the original transient vibration time-domain signal and its equivalent STFT. The evolution of the main frequency components evolves linearly with the supply frequency. Nevertheless, the amplitude of the different harmonics change during the evolution due to the mechanical attenuation or accentuation. Two components are particularly accentuated during the start-up transient, corresponding to two PSH in the $\nu = 4, 6$ locations. This resonant region is

Fig. 5. Vibration signal at rated slip and healthy conditions (a) time domain, (b) time-frequency domain

highlighted in figure 5 (b) by a shadowed area.

A novel time-frequency feature extraction algorithm is proposed in order to quantify the fault severity. It is based on the accurate amplitude sampling over the analytically computed PSH trajectories. The extracted signal profile is then averaged to discriminate among slow and fast dynamics. In the present work, only PSH+4 and PSH+6 are studied since they present the highest amplitudes and cross resonant structural regions during the transient evolution. Initially, the profile line is defined by estimating two points in the time-frequency plane. Figure 5 (b) shows the points defining the target line trajectories. The y-coordinate of both P2 is defined by equation 1 while the same coordinate of P1 is arbitrarily defined (i.e., in this case 50 Hz). The definition of the x-coordinate poses increased complexity since each studied signal starts at a different time point. For shake of simplicity, the x-coordinates are manually selected to maximize the amplitude profile.

Figure 6 exemplifies the target trajectory extraction and shows the raw sampled amplitudes for each machine fault state. The x-axis of figures 6 (b) and (c) are defined in the frequency domain to better track the resonant frequency band. The raw signals do not offer significant insights for fault discrimination. Nevertheless, some heavy oscillations can be identified in figure 6 (c) in the frequency band between 400 and 550 Hz corresponding to the severe asymmetry case. Further information is extracted by separating the slow and fast

Fig. 6. (a) STFT of the healthy specimen for rated slip conditions with sampled PSH trajectories, (b) PSH+6 raw sampled amplitude, (c) PSH+4 raw sampled amplitude

signal dynamics. This is achieved by implementing a moving average over the extracted signal with a window width of 10% the full length of the signal. Figure 7 shows the decomposition of low and fast signal dynamics for PSH+4 and PSH+6. An immediate observation is the overall reduction of the slow evolving dynamic for increased levels of asymmetry. Thus, the maximum amplitude in the resonant frequency band (i.e., between 300 Hz and 400 Hz) represents a feasible asymmetry fault indicator. The extracted oscillations do not clearly evidence the expected slip oscillations at $2s f$. Nevertheless, some heavy oscillations are observed for the severe asymmetry case between 400 Hz and 550 Hz.

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The present paper introduces a novel methodology to diagnose winding asymmetries by utilizing transient radial vibration signals in inverter-fed WRIMs. First, the physical

Fig. 7. (a) PSH+6 and (b) PSH+4 averaged trajectory amplitudes, (a) PSH+6 and (b) PSH+4 oscillations

motivation of the proposed diagnosis is discussed. Then, the studied WRIM specimen and experimental set-up is presented. The analysis of well-known steady-state vibration indicators is closely analysed to evidence the differences between light and severe asymmetry levels. Finally, the proposed methodology is introduced with the further analysis of the method outcomes.

The objective of this exploratory research is the proposition of a transient diagnosis technique that further increases diagnosis reliability. The main contribution lays on the exploitation of different mechanical frequency bands, at which fault signature may amplify or attenuate. In addition, the introduction of physics-based time-frequency feature extraction, characterized by analytically estimated trajectories, constitutes a novel quantification methodology that is independent of the specific time-frequency transformation technique. One primary limitation of this laboratory case study is the use of a rigid mechanical coupling between the WRIM and SG, potentially introducing mechanical oscillations that mask the fault signature. Addi-

tionally, the influence of the load needs to be addressed as an immediate research step. Future research should also include a thorough sensitivity analysis of the trajectory sampling and a clear, unambiguous definition of the x-coordinates. Finally, the methodology should be tested in higher power machines with different start-up modes (e.g., high inertia directly-fed WRIMs), which may represent a more realistic industrial case study.

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